

Repeating Decimals when dividing with 3 and 9 and the Proof of $0.999... = 1$

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Abstract

This paper explores the recurring patterns that arise when dividing numbers by 3, 9, 99, and other denominators composed entirely of nines and threes. It examines both single-digit and multi-digit numerators, demonstrating that the decimal expansions often yield repeating sequences. Through a series of examples, this work establishes the equivalence of $0.999...$ and 1 using multiple proofs and extends these patterns to higher numbers. Additionally, the paper discusses how the repeating decimal pattern persists when dividing by larger powers of 9 and 3 (i.e. 99,999... and 33,333...), providing a generalized approach to understanding such fractions. The findings reveal the consistency in repeating decimal behaviour, offering insights into rational number representation and decimal approximations.

Introduction

The study of repeating decimals provides a fascinating insight into number theory, revealing elegant patterns when simple fractions are converted into their decimal forms. A particularly interesting case is the equivalence of $0.999...$ and 1, which has been a topic of debate and discussion in mathematical circles. This paper aims to elucidate this equivalence by examining various division scenarios, starting with divisions by 3 and 9 and extending to more complex cases involving numbers such as 99 and 999.

Through systematic exploration, we demonstrate that when dividing numbers less than the denominator, the resulting decimal expansions display predictable repeating sequences. This observation is not only limited to single-digit numerators but also applies to larger numbers, which can be expressed in mixed fraction form. Moreover, we extend these ideas to situations where the numerator is adjusted to match the number of digits in the denominator, showing that the pattern of repeating decimals holds for any fraction where the denominator consists entirely of nines.

By analyzing these cases, this paper not only reinforces the mathematical equivalence of 0.999 and 1 but also uncovers a broader framework for understanding the behavior of repeating decimals in rational numbers.

Note: *The divisibility tricks and patterns presented in this paper are original contributions based on the author's independent observations and reasoning. While similar methods might exist in the*

mathematical literature, the techniques outlined here were developed without reference to any prior work.

Dividing by 9

(i) Single-Digit Numerators

When a single-digit number is divided by 9, a distinct pattern emerges in the resulting decimal representation. The decimal expansion consists of a repeating sequence that corresponds to the original numerator. Below are examples that illustrate this pattern for different single-digit numerators:

$$\frac{1}{9} = 0.111111\dots$$

$$\frac{6}{9} = 0.666666\dots$$

$$\frac{2}{9} = 0.222222\dots$$

$$\frac{7}{9} = 0.777777\dots$$

$$\frac{3}{9} = 0.333333\dots$$

$$\frac{8}{9} = 0.888888\dots$$

$$\frac{4}{9} = 0.444444\dots$$

$$\frac{5}{9} = 0.555555\dots$$

As seen above, dividing any single-digit number (where $1 \leq n \leq 8$) by 9 results in a repeating decimal with n as the repeated digit. This sequence highlights the cyclic nature of division by 9. If we extend this pattern to $\frac{9}{9}$ we obtain,

$$\frac{9}{9} = 0.99999\dots = 1$$

$$\therefore 0.99999\dots = 1$$

This demonstrates that the repeating decimal $0.9999\dots$ is indeed equal to 1. The equivalence can be understood as a result of the infinite repetition of 9 in the decimal, which approaches the value of 1 as closely as desired. Thus, $0.9999\dots = 1$, providing a straightforward proof for this well-known mathematical result.

(ii) Multiple-Digit Numerators

When dividing a number with multiple digits by 9, the result can be expressed as a mixed number, consisting of a whole number and a proper fraction. The decimal representation is then formed by combining the whole number with the repeating decimal corresponding to the proper fraction.

For example, consider the division of 3241 by 9:

$$\frac{3241}{9} = 360 \frac{1}{9}$$

Here, $3241 \div 9 = 360$ with a remainder of 1. The remainder forms the proper fraction $\frac{1}{9}$, which can be expressed as the repeating decimal $0.1111\dots$. Thus, we can rewrite the division result as:

$$\frac{3241}{9} = 360 \frac{1}{9} = 360 + 0.111\dots = 360.111\dots$$

$$\therefore \frac{3241}{9} = 360.1111\dots$$

This method can be applied to any multi-digit number, converting it into a combination of its whole number quotient and a repeating decimal derived from the remainder over 9. This approach illustrates the predictable behaviour of decimal expansions when dividing by 9.

Dividing by Higher Numbers like 99, 999, etc.

When dividing by numbers consisting entirely of nines, such as 99, 999, and so on, a pattern similar to the division by 9 emerges. The key is to make the number of digits in the numerator match the number of nines in the denominator. If necessary, leading zeros can be added to the numerator. This approach guarantees that the resulting decimal representation will be a repeating sequence.

For example, consider dividing 45 by 999:

1. **Matching the Number of Digits:** Since the denominator, 999, has three digits, we should express 45 with three digits by adding a leading zero, resulting in 045. This ensures that the number of digits in the numerator matches the number of nines in the denominator.
2. **Now repeat the digits like we did with 9.**

$$\frac{45}{999} = \frac{045}{999} = 0.045045045\dots$$

1. The result is a repeating decimal where the sequence "045" repeats indefinitely.

This pattern holds true for any fraction where the denominator consists solely of nines (such as 99, 999, 9999, etc.). In general, for a fraction of the form $\frac{N}{\underbrace{99\dots9}_{n \text{ times}}}$ where N has fewer

than or equal to n digits, the decimal expansion will be a repeating sequence of the digits of N.

Examples:

- $\frac{23}{99} = 0.232323\dots$
- $\frac{5}{99} = 0.050505\dots$
- $\frac{170}{999} = 0.170170\dots$

Another Proof that 0.999...=1

To further demonstrate that 0.999... is indeed equal to 1, consider the case of dividing 99 by 99:

$$99/99=1$$

Now, let's decompose 99 into two parts: 90 and 9, and divide each part by 99 separately.

1. Divide 90 by 99:

$$90/99=0.909090909\dots$$

This yields a repeating decimal of 0.909090909

2. Divide 9 by 99:

$$9/99=0.0909090909\dots$$

This gives a repeating decimal of 0.0909090909...

Now, add these two results together:

$$90/99+9/99=0.909090909\dots+0.0909090909\dots=0.999999999\dots$$

Since we started with $99/99=1$, it follows that:

$$0.999999999\dots= 1$$

Thus, this provides another clear proof that 0.999... is indeed equal to 1.

Dividing by 3

When we divide a number less than 3 by 3, the result will always be a repeating decimal. For any number n , where $1 \leq n < 3$, we can represent the division as: $n/3$

Let's examine the patterns that emerge when dividing different numbers by 3:

1. Single-Digit Numerators:

- When dividing numbers from 1 to 2 by 3, the resulting decimal is a repeating sequence based on the original number:
- $1/3=0.3333\dots$
- $2/3=0.6666\dots$
- If we consider $3/3$, it equals: $3/3=0.9999\dots=1$
- This demonstrates that $0.9999\dots$ is indeed equivalent to 1, similar to the pattern found when dividing by 9.

2. (N>3)-Digit Numerators:

- For numbers with more than one digit, we can follow the same approach used for 9 by converting the division into a mixed number (whole number + proper fraction).
- For example, let's consider $7/3$: $7/3=2+1/3=2+0.3333\dots=2.3333\dots$ This method can be generalized for any larger numbers divided by 3.

So, the general form for $n/3$, can be written as: $n/3=0.3n\dots$

Dividing by Higher Numbers like 33, 333, etc.

When dividing by numbers consisting entirely of nines, such as 33,333, and so on, a pattern similar to the division by 3 emerges. The key is to make the number of digits in the numerator match the number of nines in the denominator. If necessary, leading zeros can be added to the numerator. This approach guarantees that the resulting decimal representation will be a repeating sequence.

For example, consider dividing 45 by 333:

- 3. Matching the Number of Digits:** Since the denominator, 333, has three digits, we should express 45 with three digits by adding a leading zero, resulting in 045. This ensures that the number of digits in the numerator matches the number of nines in the denominator.
- 4. Now repeat the digits like we did with 9.**

$$\frac{45}{333} = \frac{045}{333} = 0.135135135\dots(45 \cdot 3 = 135)$$

2. The result is a repeating decimal where the sequence "135" repeats indefinitely.

This pattern holds true for any fraction where the denominator consists solely of nines (such as 33,333,3333, etc.). In general, for a fraction of the form $N/333\dots$ where N has fewer

than or equal to n digits, the decimal expansion will be a repeating sequence of the digits of $N \cdot 3$.

Examples:

- $\frac{23}{33} = 0.696969\dots$
- $\frac{5}{33} = 0.151515\dots$
- $\frac{170}{333} = 0.510510\dots$

Summary

The research presented in this paper systematically investigates the patterns found in repeating decimal representations when dividing by 3, 9, and larger denominators made entirely of nines:

1. Dividing by 3:

- For single-digit numerators less than 3, the results are repeating decimals: $1/3=0.3333\dots$ and $2/3=0.6666\dots$
- Extending the pattern to $3/3$, we find that $0.9999\dots=1$
- For multi-digit numerators, such as $7/3$, the division results in a mixed number with a repeating decimal component.

2. Dividing by 9:

- Single-digit divisions by 9 yield repeating decimals corresponding to the original numerator: $1/9=0.1111\dots$, $2/9=0.2222\dots$, ..., $8/9=0.8888\dots$. When extending to $9/9$, we again demonstrate that $0.9999\dots=1$.
- For larger numerators, expressing the division as a mixed number, such as $3241/9=360+1/9=360.1111\dots$, generalizes the pattern.

3. Additional Proof for $0.999\dots = 1$:

- By decomposing $99/99$ into $90/99+9/99$, we show that their sum equals $0.9999\dots$, reinforcing that $0.9999\dots=1$.

4. Dividing by Larger Powers of 9 and 3:

- The paper extends the repeating decimal pattern to higher powers of 9 and 3 (e.g., 99, 999, etc. and 33,333, etc.).

- For instance, $45/999$ can be expressed as $0.045045045\dots$, and $45/333$ can be expressed as $0.135135\dots$ (as $45 \cdot 3 = 135$) showing that the repeating sequence follows the numerator's digits or triple the numerator's digits.

Overall, this research demonstrates the consistency in repeating decimal patterns and provides multiple proofs for the equality of $0.999\dots$ and 1 . The results contribute to a deeper understanding of rational number representations and highlight the elegance of mathematical patterns in number theory.

These findings illustrate the consistency and elegance in repeating decimal patterns when dividing by powers of 9 , providing multiple proofs for the equivalence of $0.999\dots$ and 1 , while also highlighting the general behaviour of fractions with repeating decimal representations.

Conclusion

This paper has systematically explored the behavior of repeating decimals when dividing numbers by 3 , 9 , and higher powers of 9 , providing a clear understanding of the recurring patterns that emerge. The research demonstrated that when single-digit or multi-digit numbers are divided by these specific denominators, the resulting decimal expansions show consistent repeating sequences. The paper also presented multiple proofs confirming the equivalence of $0.999\dots$ and 1 , reinforcing a well-known result in number theory.

The findings of this paper contribute to a deeper understanding of rational numbers and their decimal approximations, highlighting the elegance and consistency of number theory. This work also serves as a foundational step for future studies on repeating decimals and their applications in fields such as mathematical analysis and computer algorithms.

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